

JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.2

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partners:
INSA (36), ISS (27)

Contributing partners:
All partners

JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.2

JIP06-WP2-T2.1 Genome analyses

JIP06-WP2- sub-task ST2.1.2 Harmonisation sampling and methods NGS

D.2.1.2 Report on the comparisons of variants and reference sample exchange

Description of the task

The two main overall operational objectives of COVRIN WP2 are: i) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2; ii) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2.

Within WP2, **Task 2.1 is focused on the analyses of whole genome sequences of SARS-CoV-2 strains circulating in humans and animals**. In particular, Task 2.1. involves **methodologies exchange** among partners [from wet-lab Next-generation sequencing (NGS)-related procedures to Bioinformatics pipelines], as well as **phylogenetic analysis and investigation for potential virulence traits** (e.g., mutations known to play a direct role in receptor binding or antibody recognition). This approach aims not only at **promoting protocol sharing/harmonization**, but also at **mapping evolutionary changes of SARS-CoV-2 viruses isolated within and across human and different animal species**, as a means to identify mutations and recombination events driving adaptation to alternative hosts. In parallel, this task also supports the selection of strains that may be used for downstream biological characterization *in vivo* and *in vitro*.

This deliverable describes the activities and first outcomes of the **sub-task ST2.1.2 (Harmonisation sampling and methods NGS)**.

Description of the deliverable

A Bioinformatics Ring Trial was carried out in order to assess the reproducibility of bioinformatics pipelines (i.e., from raw reads to consensus sequences, using reference-based mapping) currently being applied for genome analyses of SARS-CoV-2 (and other coronaviruses - CoV) across the partners institutes. For this, the partners responsible for organizing this Ring Trial (INSA and ISS) collected sequence raw data from partners particularly enrolled in Task T2.1 (ANSES, INSA, ISS, IZSAM and APHA) and from public repositories.

The selected dataset (detailed in Table 1) was built in order to cover:

- i) different wet-lab protocols and NGS technologies [Ion Torrent (S5 and Genexus), Illumina (MiSeq and NextSeq 550) and Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT)];
- ii) different quality levels (namely, regarding sequencing depth of coverage);
- iii) genetic diversity, including sequences from variants of interest (VOI) / concern (VOC);
- iv) samples with specific features likely informative in the context of the trial, such as confirmed VOC/non-VOC mixed infection, artificial reads with multiple VOC-associated mutations (SNPs and indels), SARS-CoV-2 evolved during experimental evolution [1] or during a long-term infection in an immunocompromised individual [2].

In total, 27 anonymized raw reads sets were included in the dataset and made downloadable from a shared folder:

- i) 19 SARS-CoV-2 fastq.gz files obtained from the partners (one of which artificial);

- ii) 3 SARS-CoV-2 fastq.gz files obtained from the CDC Benchmark datasets for WGS analysis of SARS-CoV-2 (<https://github.com/CDCgov/datasets-sars-cov-2>) representing the same original sample processed by different wet-lab approaches and sequenced using two different platforms;
- iii) 5 fastq.gz files from other CoV species (to be run optionally by the participants), namely two from Porcine epidemic diarrhea virus, one from Avian infectious bronchitis virus and two from Erinaceus CoV.

The participants were also provided with the sample list (simplified version of Table 1), templates for two report tables (pipeline details and results summary) and reference sequences (fasta format) to be used for mapping.

In the scope of the Bioinformatics Ring Trial, the participant partners were asked to provide:

- i) the consensus sequences (fasta format) reconstructed from each of the 27 raw read sets;
- ii) a table with details of the pipelines used (quality cut-offs, options, parameters per NGS technology, etc.);
- iii) a summary table with the list of the consensus sequences sent and reasons for any that were not provided (if applicable).

The partners were also asked to provide (optionally) the list of mutations, minor variants list, and Pango lineage classification.

Responses were obtained from eight COVRIN partners, **INSA (36), ISS (27), ANSES (01), APHA (21), FLI (10), INIAV (35), IZSAM (28), Sciensano (04), with the latter replying from two separate laboratories.** Several of the participant partners did not send the mandatory output tables (or these were sent with incomplete data) and one partner did not provide the mandatory consensus sequences. As such, the comparative analysis (as described in Methods and Results) relied exclusively on the consensus sequences obtained from seven partners and focused on exploring the differences (SNPs, indels, "N" content) among the several consensus sequences generated from the same sample (see Results). The extra data (i.e, not sequence data) provided by partners was only used for results interpretation and discussion, where possible.

Methods

The goal of this exercise was to explore the reproducibility of pipelines and identify critical bioinformatics analysis aspects of reference-based viral genome reconstruction, rather than ranking the pipelines (which were kept fully anonymous) in regard to the "right answer". As such, as there was no "correct" consensus sequence to compare the partners results against, the comparative analysis focused on retrieving several metrics that could be informative about both the congruence between sequences generated from the same sample raw data and the pipelines settings/criteria justifying the observed discrepancies.

For each sample, two types of alignment have been produced: i) an alignment of the consensus sequences produced by partners with the reference sequence (alignment 1 – used for most comparisons), and ii) pairwise alignments between each consensus sequence and the reference sequence (alignment 2 – used for a fine assessment of insertions/deletions). The alignments were obtained using MAFFT v7.475 [3] and further visually inspected using Aliview [4] and manually curated. This curation was particularly important to minimize the impact of a few main issues identified in some pipelines (see Results) on the SNP distance calculations.

A first inspection of the alignments revealed an excess of nucleotide differences at the 5' and 3' ends of the genome sequences. As these regions are prone to sequencing errors due to low coverage (also, in

SARS-CoV-2, the pre-NGS whole-genome amplification does not cover these regions) they were deleted (as routinely done for SARS-CoV-2 phylogenetics), in order to avoid misalignment and subsequent overestimation of SNP distances (see Results). These deleted ambiguous positions were 0-104 and 29834-29903 in SARS-CoV-2 (NC_045512.2); 0-11 in reference AY851295 (Avian infectious bronchitis virus); and 0-21 and 30121-30148 in reference NC_039207 (Betacoronavirus Erinaceus).

For each consensus sequence, the following metrics were assessed (as reported in Table 2):

- 1) SNP distance to the reference using the alignment 1;
- 2) Number of ACGT bases;
- 3) Number of masked nucleotides (reported as “N” or “n”);
- 4) Number of insertions to the reference (alignment 2), and their summed total length;
- 5) Number of deletions to the reference (alignment 2), and their summed total length;
- 6) Number of degenerated bases;

For a better comparison of the differences among the several consensus sequences generated from each sample, the individual consensus results (Table 2) were condensed, and further metrics were assessed (as reported in Table 3):

- 1) Minimum, median and maximum, SNP distances to the reference (alignment 1);
- 2) Minimum, maximum and median pairwise SNP distances between consensus sequences (alignment 1, excluding reference from analysis);
- 3) Minimum and maximum number of ACTG bases;
- 4) Minimum and maximum of number of masked positions (“N”) and the median excluding outlier (minimum and maximum) values;
- 5) Number of consensus sequences with insertions, as well as the minimum, maximum and median number of insertions observed.
- 6) Number of consensus sequences with deletions, as well as the minimum, maximum and median number of deletions observed;
- 7) Minimum and maximum number of degenerated bases;
- 8) List of Pango lineages obtained per sample and respective number of sequences per lineage.

The pairwise SNP distances were calculated as number of differences using MEGAX [5]. The length of the consensus, the number of N bases, insertions, deletions, degenerated bases (i.e., non-ACTG nucleotides) and minimum, maximum and median values have been calculated using ad hoc Python scripts (https://github.com/lucadesabato/COVRIN_taskT2.1_scripts). Lineage assignments were performed using Phylogenetic Assignment of Named Global Outbreak Lineages (Pangolin) (cov-lineages.org) (<https://pangolin.cog-uk.io/>), version 3.1.19.

Data availability

The accession numbers of the raw reads used in this trial are indicated in Table 1 (when publicly available). All the consensus sequences received, along with the alignments used for comparative analysis (with the exception of sample 26), as well as Tables 1-3 are available in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6458215>).

Results and Discussion

In total, 176 consensus sequences (see Supplementary data) were received from the participating partners, with only 3 out of 8 partners (herein randomly anonymized as partners/pipeline A to H) sending sequences for all the 27 samples. Several reasons were indicated by the partners for not sending some of the sequences, such as:

- i) sample(s) did not pass quality criteria for consensus generation;
- ii) the partner(s) pipeline(s) did not handle all sequencing technologies (e.g. ONT-only pipeline);
- iii) the partner(s) pipeline(s) does(do) not generate consensus sequences;

iv) the partner(s) pipeline(s) only fit(s) SARS-CoV-2 sequence data.

In some cases, no reasons were specified for the absent sequences. Overall, 4 to 8 consensus sequences were available for comparison for each of the 27 samples.

As detailed in Methods and in Tables 2 and 3, the sequences generated from the same sample (i.e., same input read data) were compared using several metrics.

SARS-CoV-2

Lineage assignment

In general, a good congruence was obtained regarding the Pango classification for SARS-CoV-2 samples (samples 1 to 22), with all the consensus sequences generated for 15/22 samples having the same classification per sample (Table 2). For the remaining seven SARS-CoV-2 samples, the classification was still consistent across sequences with no more than two sequences with discrepant classifications. These cases included “None” classification or classification into an ancestral/sub-lineage and were mainly linked to an excess of undefined nucleotides (“N”) and/or short length sequences (known to be the main reasons for misclassification). A notable exception regards a sequence (from sample 18) with an excess of “degenerated” bases (i.e., non-ACTG nucleotides).

N content and insertions/deletions

Despite the overall congruence observed in lineage classification, which is one of the key outputs of routine surveillance, three main issues were observed across the sequences generated by three pipelines:

- i) one pipeline (A) yielded an excess of “N” (Figure 1A);
- ii) one pipeline (G) did not perform indel calling (Figure 1B and 1C);
- iii) one pipeline (E) did not insert “N” (commonly used to label low coverage regions) but instead inserted “---” (commonly used to label deletions in nucleotide alignments).

These issues would mostly likely render the derived sequences unsuitable for some downstream analysis (e.g., phylogenetics, functional analysis, protein modeling, etc.) and largely complicated the analysis and interpretation of the results of this exercise. For instance, the sequences enriched with false deletions (e.g., derived from pipeline E) largely complicated the alignment of the consensus sequences and, in the absence of vcf files, it was not always possible to define the exact regions called as a deletion by the pipeline.

The three issues led to huge discrepancies in the comparisons of “N” and/or indel content across sequences from the same sample (Tables 2 and 3) and ultimately jeopardized a more comprehensive assessment of the pipelines reproducibility for these metrics. This hurdle was further enhanced by the lack of response by some partners to requested information about the pipeline settings (namely, minimum horizontal coverage, minimum vertical coverage and frequency for mutation validation and criteria for “N” masking) and also because some pipelines automatically downsized some heavier raw data files. Nonetheless, our comparative analysis allowed us to infer that very different behaviors were adopted to deal with low coverage regions (including, the 5’ and 3’ end regions, that were either masked with “N” or truncated). For instance, this was well illustrated by the analysis of a low coverage sample included in the dataset (sample 19) that had a mean depth of coverage ~300-fold (marked by high fluctuations, including regions of total dropout) and a horizontal coverage of ~70% (with at least 10-fold) and ~90% (with at least 1-fold coverage). Two participants (B and D) provided sequences with an “N” content (~30%) compatible with their reported coverage cut-offs for masking low coverage regions (≥10-fold). The other three participants sent sequences with a horizontal coverage (as assessed by % of ACTG nucleotides) of ~90%, implying that positions covered by as low as 1 read were validated in the consensus. Of note, one of these four participants reported a coverage cut-off that was not congruent

with the observations. Overall, these issues hampered the establishment of definitive correlations between N content *versus* low coverage regions or indel calling *versus* mutation validation criteria.

Even though, it was still possible to retrieve some general conclusions for these metrics. Among the participants that reported the coverage cut-off for masking ("N") low coverage regions, there was a good congruence between the regions masked in two of the pipelines (B and D) and their respective cut-offs. Another pipeline (F) did not show congruence between the cut-offs and "N" content and another one yielded a general excess of "N"s (pipeline A, as mentioned above) in Illumina samples, regardless of the coverage. The latter case could be linked to the use of an ONT-oriented pipeline to analyse Illumina data.

Regarding insertions/deletions, the highest number of insertions was mainly observed in sequences generated by pipeline E, especially for ONT and Ion Torrent samples (indeed, the maximum number of insertions in these samples was always linked to this pipeline) (Figure 1B and Table 3). This can be justified by the low (1-read) minimum depth of coverage applied by this pipeline to validate a mutation (regardless of sequencing technology) and higher error rate of ONT and Ion torrent, especially in homopolymeric tracts (where pipeline E mostly reported insertions). In contrast, this 1-read cut-off minimized the expected detrimental impact of inserting gaps in low coverage regions (instead of N) in the discrepancies at deletions level. In fact, there was still some congruence in the deletions reported in 11/22 samples, where the maximum and median number (and length) of deletions was the same (Table 2), even considering that one pipeline (G) did not perform indel calling.

SNPs distance to the reference

At a first inspection, there was a noticeable excess of nucleotide differences at the 5' and 3' ends of the genome sequences. As these regions are already known to be problematic (mainly due to sequencing with low depth of coverage) and represented a transversal issue in the dataset (see methods), they were deleted from the alignments used for SNP comparisons (as routinely done for SARS-CoV-2 phylogenetics) to allow a clearer assessment of differences between sequences and pipelines.

After this "noise" removal, the assessment of SNP differences revealed that there was still some degree of variation in SNP distance to the reference genome between the sequences derived from each sample, even though there was a general good congruence among Illumina samples (especially in pipelines B to F) (Table 2 and Figure 3). In fact, many pipelines reported exactly the same number of SNPs to the reference (as also supported by the overall high congruence in lineage assignment), although there was only one sample (sample 20) for which all the pipelines detected the same number of SNPs. Notably, sample 20 is the only artificial sample in the dataset, so its "clean" profile (homogenous coverage throughout genome and 100% frequency of all simulated mutations) should explain the highest concordance. The large discrepancies observed in the other samples (Figure 3) were mostly linked to:

- i) the main issues stated above, since, for instance, a low number of SNPs was frequently associated with the pipeline yielding an excess of "N" (pipeline A) (Table 3);
- ii) Sequencing technology, with higher discrepancies for ONT followed by Ion Torrent (even though this trend was exacerbated by the use of pipelines unsuitable to handle these technologies);
- iii) and, as expected, to the sample with low and uneven coverage (as expected and illustrated by sample 19, discussed above).

Pairwise SNP distance

Notwithstanding, despite the differences in the SNP distances to the reference genome, the median pairwise SNP distances was low (ranging between 0 and 3 SNPs) for the 22 SARS-CoV-2 samples (Table 2 and Figures 2 and 3). In particular, for 10 out of the 22 SARS-CoV-2 samples, all the pairwise distances were equal to 0, meaning that the SNP differences to the reference observed between sequences are due to distinct "N" content (i.e., low coverage regions) rather than to distinct SNP calls for the same nucleotide positions. Among the remaining 12 SARS-CoV-2 samples, the highest discrepancies in pairwise SNP distances were observed in ONT samples, followed by Ion Torrent and Illumina samples (Figure 2B and 3).

Although ONT is associated with an intrinsic higher error rate (particularly, when compared with Illumina), these high pairwise distances were linked to specific pipelines/partners, especially to pipeline E, that applies very low (1-read) minimum depth of coverage to validate a mutation, regardless of sequencing technology, and C, that was reported not to be optimized to deal with ONT data. For instance, in sample 4, pipeline C yielded a sequence diverging up to 23 SNPs from the other sequences. Another notable example stands for sample 6 where the sequences from partners C and E had 12 SNP distance from each other, but 0-1 SNPs to the other consensus. This is explained by the fact that these SNPs occurred in regions where the other sequences contained “N”, so, again, the miscalls were due to the validation of mutations by these two pipelines in poorly covered regions. Despite the expected higher congruence associated with Illumina samples, these observations highlighted the need to choose and/or adjust pipelines parameters/cut-offs to deal with distinct technologies (as reported by some partners). This same issue also biased the insertions/deletions calling, as illustrated in Figure 2C and 2D and described above.

Other particularities

Same sample sequenced with three approaches

This exercise included three samples (10, 12 and 17) representing the same original sample processed by different wet-lab approaches and sequenced at two platforms (retrieved from <https://github.com/CDCgov/datasets-sars-cov-2>) to assess if the same pipeline finds virtually no differences between them. Seven participants provided consensus sequences for the three samples, with the exception of partner H that only processed ONT data (samples 10 and 12). Five of the seven participants reported sequences with no more than 2 SNPs between each other, with only three of these having 0 SNP differences between the 2-3 sequences (Table 3 and Figure 3). The other two participants with highly discrepant results (C and E) reported sequences diverging up to 13 SNPs (including SNPs called in low coverage regions). This is most likely due to the issues identified above for these two pipelines.

VOC/non-VOC mixed infection

One of the samples (sample 18) corresponded to a confirmed coinfection enrolling two lineages: Alpha (B.1.1.7) and B.1.177 at ~80% and ~20% within-patient frequency, respectively. Only two participants reported (as requested) that this sample represented a lineages admixture. In one case, the admixture was flagged and the consensus was provided but with the indication that it would be rejected by the pipeline, while, in the other case, this sample was flagged due to the discrepancies obtained in Pango (B.1) and Nextclade (Alpha) classifications. Further inspection of this consensus showed that the classification discrepancies were due to “N” masking of several positions distinguishing the two lineages (i.e., positions with “allelic” mixture). Interestingly, among the other participants not reporting this admixture, there was one sequence (also classified as B.1) with 48 degenerated bases (mostly falling in those mixed nucleotide positions), which shows that this pipeline (G) also has the potential to automatically identify mixed infections. Except for the two B.1 sequences, all the other five consensus sequences had the same 19 SNPs and 4 deletions to the reference (Table 3 and Figure 3), meaning that these pipelines reconstructed the genome of the dominant lineage in the admixture (B.1.1.7).

SARS-CoV-2 evolved during experimental evolution and during a long-term infection in an immunocompromised individual

Two of the samples included in the dataset, sample 8 (SARS-CoV-2 from experimental evolution in Vero cells) and sample 13 (long-term infection in an immunocompromised individual), are characterized by large *inframe* deletions in Spike:

- Sample 8: 21 bp (genome position 23596-23616; Spike amino acids 679-685) deletion in furin cleavage site as typically seen in SARS-CoV-2 propagated in Vero cells [1];

- Sample 13: 39 bp (genome position 21610–21648; Spike amino acids 18-30) and 12 bp (genome position 21983–21994; Spike amino acids 141-144).

Notably, with the exception of participant G (that did not perform indel calling in any sample), all the other participants identified the deletions in these samples (despite a slight difference in deletion length observed in one sequence in each sample).

Emerging mutation of interest S:E484K

One of the samples (sample 9) included an emerging mutation of interest in Spike (G23012A; amino acid change E484K) at ~52% frequency. Three participants reported this mutation in the consensus sequences (B, C and E), two participants inserted a degenerated nucleotide (D and G) and the other two inserted the reference base (A and F) which reflects the frequency cut-off values of 0.9 and 0.7 to call a nucleotide applied by these pipelines.

Other coronaviruses

Five additional samples corresponding to other coronaviruses (samples 23-27) were also included in this exercise (Table 1) although their analysis was optional. Between 4 and 5 participants provided consensus sequences for each sample (Tables 2 and 3). The reference sequences provided for mapping were closely related to the target virus in three samples (24 to 26), while the Betacoronavirus Erinaceus reads set (samples 23 and 27) differed >2000 SNPs from the reference sequence. Globally, the main conclusions of the comparative analysis did not differ much from those observed for the SARS-CoV-2 samples. Very high congruence was observed for the only Illumina sample (Sample 26) (Table 2). This was not unexpected because it was a high quality sample and the participants (B to F) providing sequences for this sample were the ones with the highest congruence for Illumina samples in the SARS-CoV-2 dataset (Figure 3). Among the four Ion Torrent samples, the highest congruence was seen for the samples mapped against closely related references (samples 24 and 25). Indeed, the other two (23 and 27), representing samples sequenced following the SISPA protocol, reached very high pairwise SNP distances. Nevertheless, while the use of a divergent reference genome certainly contributed to some discrepancies, it does not fully justify the observed differences. In fact, much of the pairwise differences observed were, not only, due to the validation of mutations in poorly covered regions by some of the pipelines (as was concluded for SARS-CoV-2 samples), but also due to one pipeline (G) that inserted the reference sequence in these low/no coverage regions (which, given the divergence of the reference sequence used, led to large pairwise distances). While for SARS-CoV-2 this issue might not be so evident (as the reference genome is still very closely related to sequenced virus), it is critical to apply a more conservative approach (more strict coverage cut-offs to validate a mutation as well as to have a strategy to mask low/coverage regions), especially when leading with samples where the divergence of the target virus (both in SNPs and indels) to the reference genome used is unknown.

Concluding remarks

On behalf of the COVRIN project (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-covrin/>), we conducted a Bioinformatics Ring Trial mainly focused on assessing whether the bioinformatics pipelines being applied for genome analyses of SARS-CoV-2 by COVRIN partners generate concordant consensus sequences from the same raw read data and further exploring the main reasons behind the discrepancies. Overall, there was a good congruence in Pango lineage assignment between consensus sequences provided by the different participants for the 22 SARS-CoV-2 samples. Still, a few critical issues identified in some pipelines (Figure 1) challenged the comparative analysis and discussion of the results, namely insertion of “gaps” in low coverage regions instead of “N” masking, absence of indel calling and inadequacy of the pipeline to the sequencing technology. These issues would most likely render the derived sequences

unsuitable for some downstream analysis (e.g., phylogenetics, functional analysis, protein modeling, etc.) and, in this exercise, were in the base of most discrepancies observed between sequences of the same sample in, for instance, N content, pairwise SNP distance, SNP and indel differences against the reference. Although the sequencing technologies (with distinct intrinsic error rates) may have had influence on some discrepancies (Figure 2), we concluded that discordant results were mostly linked to those critical issues stated above, as well as to the mis-adjustment of key pipeline parameters, namely, the minimum depth of coverage per site to validate a mutation (which was reported, or inferred from the data, to be as low as 1-fold in some pipelines). These observations consolidate the need to promote training in applied bioinformatics and raise awareness about technical aspects of data analysis to avoid such critical errors, reinforcing the need of tailoring the bioinformatics pipeline / parameters according to the sequencing technology, scope of the sequencing (e.g., rapid lineage circulation assessment or in-depth outbreak tracking) or other data characteristics (namely, which wet-lab protocol was used to produce the read data).

This exercise also allowed us to conclude that some key technical aspects would greatly benefit from harmonization. For instance, some partners applied distinct strategies to deal with the 5' and 3' ends, by either truncating or "N" masking them, while others had no criteria to handle these error prone regions. Contrarily to other settings (discussed below), this issue is a good target for international harmonization. As seen in this exercise, the comparison analysis was only possible after ends masking because, otherwise, the "noise" from these regions would render considerable SNP distances and ultimately hamper reaching comprehensive conclusions about the main reasons behind the discrepancies.

The depth of coverage cut-off applied to identify and mask low coverage regions is a pivotal parameter to define in this kind of analysis. Although a strict, internationally agreed, cut-off is likely not achievable, the choice of adequate thresholds cannot be disregarded and, ideally, must be again tailored to the sequencing technology and to other factors (such as, the ultimate goal of the analysis). In fact, setting (error-prone) non-conservative cut-offs (e.g., consensus generation in regions with coverage as low as 1-fold) should definitely be avoided as it potentiates the insertion of SNP and indel errors, as clearly illustrated in this exercise.

Another key software parameter is the minimum frequency to validate a mutation. While, again, this choice of a "unique" cut-off is not expected to be smoothly harmonized at international level, users must be aware of the implications of choosing a given value instead of another. For instance, choosing a conservative higher cut-off value (e.g., 70% or 90%, as commonly performed) might be accompanied by other parallel metrics which avoids the loss of emerging mutation identification (such as the ~52% E484K mutation in sample 9). On the other hand, the adoption of a less strict cut-off (50%, as also commonly performed), which would allow capturing this emerging mutation (as seen in this exercise), should not neglect the eventually high potential to incorporate SNPs with lower read support. Other specific add-values were achieved by the introduction of samples with some particularities in this exercise, such as a sample reflecting a VOC/non-VOC mixed infection that was not identified by most partners. Although most pipelines could reconstruct a consensus corresponding to the genome of the dominant lineage in the admixture (because the minor lineage was at ~20% frequency), the results showed that there are several available technical approaches to allow pipelines to flag these "mixed infection" cases by identifying SNP sites with "allelic" mixture (e.g., systematic screening of these mix positions in vcf files or introduction of degenerated bases in these positions followed by automatic flag of excess of non-ATCG sites). In fact, a blind generation of consensus sequences without extra flags leads to such "admixture" cases being overlooked.

There are some limitations associated with this exercise. In order to potentiate the partners participation in the ring trial (and considering that most partners were involved in pandemic-related activities), it was established that the partners and pipelines would be anonymized and only a few mandatory files would be requested. A priori, this implied a less in-depth analysis and interpretation of results. This was further limited because several pipeline details and outputs (including some mandatory but especially those "optional") were not provided by several participants. Altogether, this did not allow us to fully compare all the pipelines characteristics (some of which were instead inferred from the data) and imposed a comparative analysis mainly based on the common data provided by all participants (i.e., the consensus

sequences), thus excluding other indicators that could also be informative about the performance of the pipelines.

Nonetheless, despite all the limitations and hurdles, the bioinformatics ring trial conducted on behalf of COVRIN still turned out to be very informative and reached its main goal, i.e., to explore the congruence across pipelines, while identifying critical aspects that should be taken into account when performing reference-based viral genome reconstruction. The lessons learned can be useful to promote data analysis harmonization towards an enhanced reproducibility of results produced by laboratories performing genome analyses of viruses.

References

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Figures

Figure 1. Distribution of the “N” content (*panel A*), number of **deletions** (*panel B*) and **insertions** (*panel C*) across **all consensus sequences per participant**. Details are provided in Table 3.

Figure 2. Maximum values of four evaluated metrics observed in the 22 SARS-CoV-2 samples and their distribution by sequencing technology: A) maximum N positions, B) maximum pairwise distance, C) maximum number of insertions and D) maximum number of deletions. The 22 samples [Illumina (n=14), Ion Torrent (n=4) and ONT (n=4)] are colored by the participant/pipeline reporting the sequence with the maximum values for each sample. For the maximum pairwise distance, when more than one sequence has that pairwise distance within that sample, the dot is shown in grey; when the maximum corresponds to a sequence that also has a general discrepancy against all the other sequences, the dot has the color of the originating partner; when the maximum results from the sole discrepancy between two sequences, the dot has two colors, corresponding to the originating partners. Details are provided in Tables 2 (aggregated) and 3 (individual).

Sample	Technology	Pipelines								pairwise SNP distance	
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	max	median
2	Illumina	52	57	57	55	57	57	54	H	1	0
3		25	31	32	30	32	32	32		0	0
8		4	10	10	10	10	10	9		0	0
9		30	38	38	37	38	37	37		1	0
11		23	30	30	30	30	30	31		0	0
13		23	25	24	25	24	25	24		1	0
14		38	45	45	44	45	45	45		0	0
15		38	41	43	41	43	43	42		0	0
17*		8	8	8	8	8	8	10		0	0
18		21	36	36	36	36	36	4		3	0
19			32	42	27	42	41	40		3	1
20			22	22	22	22		22		0	0
21		24	34	34	34	34	34	34		0	0
22		26	34	34	34	34	34	34		0	0
1	Ion Torrent	13	17	17	15	16	15	15	H	2	0
5		8	9	10	9	9	9	9		1	0
7		8	9	9	9	9	9	9		0	0
16		12	18	19	18	18	17	15		4	1
4	ONT	40	40	58	41	39	1	38	41	23	1
6		35	34	41	21	38	2	7	35	11	0
10*		8	8	13	10	12		8	8	9	2
12*		8	8	10	8	8		8	8	2	0

Figure 3. Overview of the general congruence between pipelines across the 22 SARS-CoV-2 samples, in regards to SNP distance to the reference, number of deletions and number of insertions. The congruence matrix indicates the number of SNPs to the reference and is coloured as follows: **GREEN**) group of sequences that share the same SNP distance to the reference (light green), and also share the same number of deletions or insertions (darker green), OR fully share the same number of insertions and deletions (darkest green; fully congruent sequences for these three metrics); **BLUE**) group of sequences that share the same SNP distance, within a sample where another group of sequences with higher congruence (green) is present; **WHITE**) sequences with no match with other sequences in SNP distance to the reference; **GREY**) no sequence available. Details are provided in Table 3. Notes: 1) the SNP distance to the reference excludes the 5' and 3' end regions of the genome (see Methods). 2) Two sequences with distinct SNP distances to the reference do not necessarily have SNP differences between them (this might simply reflect differences in "N" content), as

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

reflected in the overall pairwise SNP distances (median and maximum). *Raw read data of samples 10, 12 and 17 were obtained from the same original sample.